

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF A UNIVERSITY TEACHER

Shoyimova Shokhista Sanakulovna

Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *The article describes the problems of the activities of teachers at the university, the tendency to emotional burnout, the study of the main components of the syndrome of emotional burnout and its impact on the educational process. In the course of the practical part of the study, the features of anxiety and emotional burnout were studied using the example of two departments, socio-psychological features that affect the occurrence of emotional burnout among teachers were identified.*

Keywords: *socio-psychological characteristics, anxiety, anxiety level, burnout syndrome, teachers.*

INTRODUCTION

The problem of the psychological well-being of a teacher is one of the most urgent problems in modern psychology of higher education. In modern conditions, the activity of a teacher is literally saturated with factors that cause professional burnout: a large number of social contacts during the working day, high responsibility, the need to comply with social norms. The professional activity of higher education teachers is distinguished by the fact that it occupies a dominant position in a person's life, often crowding out personal space and personal life. The effectiveness of professional activity is associated with the intensity of work, non-rationing of loads, emotional involvement, strict social limits and observance of moral categories.

THEORETICAL BASIS OR METHODS

Teaching activity is currently one of the low-paid professions, while being an economically little prestigious profession. In addition, in the field of education, there is a clear trend of aging personnel, especially those with a doctorate degree.

These trends undoubtedly come down to the study of the syndrome of emotional burnout, which was studied by V.V. Boyko, V.E. Orel, A.D. Demina, N.Z. Kaigorodova and others. [12-17]

RESULTS

When determining the syndrome of professional burnout of teachers at a university, it is important to determine the main components and their impact on the educational process:

1. Emotional exhaustion. Emotional involvement, brightness, charisma of a higher school teacher is a necessary arsenal of education, it not only helps students to better learn new material, activates their intellectual abilities, but also fills their lives with interesting events, promotes an active life position. With emotional exhaustion, the amount of learned material decreases sharply, interest is lost not only in the subject, but also in the learning process itself, both among students and teachers.

2. Depersonalization - a negative attitude towards a person, a negative, cynical or indifferent perception of him, develops as a defense against overwhelming emotional states as a result of treating a student as an object of professional influence. [12] Teachers with burnout

syndrome at the university are characterized by the prevalence of negative assessments and dissatisfaction with service relations.

An important component of personal attitude is anxiety. According to the author, it affects the syndrome of professional burnout and is directly related to cooperative behavior. [14] Anxiety is generated by a subjectively experienced threat. There is a frightening possibility of the following events: fear of losing self-respect, fear of “losing face” in a conflict situation or fear of “public ridicule” in a significant situation, fear of humiliation, as well as loss of love, approval, recognition from students and colleagues. This can develop into feelings of enmity towards others and towards the work in general. At the same time, the level of anxiety increases with the fear of simultaneously losing a job and reducing the load. [15]. Horney identifies four main means by which an individual tries to protect himself from basal anxiety: love, submission, power, and the reaction of withdrawal (removal) [13].

DISCUSSION

In modern conditions, the requirements for the quality of work of university teachers are significantly increasing, but the established style of their pedagogical activity does not always fully meet the modern requirements of the educational process. Therefore, the study of the style of the teacher's activity continues to be an important psychological and pedagogical task, involving the diagnosis of style, the identification of factors, conditions, ways and means of its formation and improvement.

The style of pedagogical activity (SPA) is an individual-peculiar, relatively stable system of preferred methods and methods of pedagogical interaction between a teacher and students.

In terms of content, this system is significantly conditioned by motives, attitudes, values, and meanings of pedagogical activity. It is also determined by the peculiarities of the socialization and development of the teacher as a specialist, a professional, it characterizes his social mobility, his readiness to combine his abilities as a subject of the educational process with the capabilities of the object in a real situation of pedagogical activity as harmoniously as possible.

The style of pedagogical activity is determined by the properties of various hierarchical levels of individuality - from temperament to higher levels - the value-motivational sphere, the orientation of the teacher's personality.

Internal prerequisites determine the teacher's preferred choice of specific methods of didactic interaction. At the same time, style is a formative result of the social environment, it reflects the interaction in the social system "man - man". It can be said that the style of the teacher's activity is a system of conjugation of individuality with social structures and individual subjects.

The style of pedagogical activity should not be understood as the implementation of a set of individual properties of an individual: it is an integral system formed by expedient connections, with the help of which a certain result is achieved. A universal feature of the teacher's style of activity is its stylistic unity (integrity), which characterizes the functional unity of homogeneous mental properties focused on the implementation of specific functions of activity, as well as the manifestation of style as a characteristic of pedagogical interaction in general, including preference for a stimulus, type of situation, means and methods for achieving goals, the “form” of the result, etc.

The style of pedagogical activity as a multidimensional phenomenon has its own structure. It contains and manifests itself in various combinations and ratios of various components. The most significant of them give the style a unique, individual look.

Proceeding from the fact that “the structure of a person as a subject of activity is formed from certain properties of an individual and personality, corresponding to a certain subject and means of activity” [17], the style structure is an interweaving, interpenetration of content and operational components.

The meaningful substructure of style is a complex of characteristics related to different levels of individuality, and is a hierarchical system of basic integral parameters. It includes: temperament as a biological basis, a prerequisite for the development of stylistic components, expressive-instrumental and value-semantic spheres.

It should be noted that temperament, together with the properties of the substructure of experience, only affects the style, but determine its properties that are included in the upper level of the hierarchical structure of style.

The expressive-instrumental structure characterizes the forms and methods of external manifestation of individual properties, typical for the subject, interaction with the external environment. It includes character traits; features of intelligence and abilities; the originality of the role element of the structure of the style of pedagogical activity, given by a certain system of relations, expectations and norms of social groups.

In the real activity of the teacher, all the components and substructures of style, with all their diversity, difference and inconsistency, interacting and passing into each other, form an inseparable unity of style.

The content and operational structures of style correspond to such characteristics of activity as objectivity and subjectivity [12]. They reflect the bi-determination of the style itself - from the side of the subject and the objective conditions of activity.

The formation of the style of pedagogical activity is influenced by social and individual prerequisites, but they do not determine it, but only suggest certain possibilities. The need to use certain opportunities is determined by the development of activity, the specifics of the interaction of the subject with the external conditions of professional activity. They are the main reasons that determine the formation of individual style characteristics of the teacher's personality.

The assimilation of style is largely influenced by the zone of uncertainty of activity, which arises as a result of the possibility of achieving results using various methods, means and intermediate goals. At the same time, mastering the style is associated with the choice by the teacher of such a system of preferred tasks, methods for solving them and intermediate goals that contribute to achieving the greatest success in activity and the greatest correspondence of different-level individual properties to the requirements of the environment (the so-called “phenomenon of subjectively convenient conditions for activity”).

Moreover, “the assimilation of an individual style and the development of individuality occur due to a special, as we believe, universal motive - to always remain an individuality, protect one’s individuality and become an increasingly harmonious individuality” [13].

The formation and development of an effective style of pedagogical activity of a university teacher is an important task due to the fact that it ensures the professional development of a teacher and the achievement of a high level of pedagogical skill, minimizes the negative impact of the external environment on the personality and activities of a teacher, increases his psychological stability in the process of pedagogical activity, develops in him a holistic and adequate self-assessment of the personality and activity, the desire for creativity.

CONCLUSION

Analysis of the obtained results mathematically reliably allowed us to assert that the level of anxiety in the humanities department is higher than in the technical one. Whereas the level of emotional burnout is higher in technical specialties. Specifying the psychodiagnostic results in the course of a psychological conversation, it was found that teachers of the humanities, having greater emotionality, have the skills of coinciding behavior. Teachers, suppressing emotions, quickly resolve conflict situations at the cost of professional burnout.

Thus, it is possible to single out socio-psychological features that influence the occurrence of burnout syndrome among university teachers:

- democratic transformations that led to the disruption of relationships between participants in the educational process;
- unpredictability of new changes in the field of education, both in the educational process and in the structure itself;
- the nature of professional teaching activity: the need for empathy, sympathy, moral responsibility for students;
- congestion of the working week; low wages; the intense nature of the work;
- official troubles; dissatisfaction with work: lack of a clear connection between the learning process and the result obtained, the discrepancy between the results and the effort expended;
- the presence of conflicts vertically and horizontally; the difficulty of solving difficult situations with students and university administration;
- inability to regulate their own emotional situations; dissatisfaction with their self-realization in various life and professional situations.

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